

Brain-Computer Interface Technology —Direct Communication Between Brain and Computer—

*Simon Kojima⁽¹⁾

(1) Functional Control Systems, Graduate School of Engineering and Science, Shibaura
Institute of Technology, Saitama, Japan.

*Corresponding author: nb21106@shibaura-it.ac.jp

The brain-computer interface gives users control and communication pathways that do not depend on peripheral nerves and muscles. It has been studied primarily for patients who have neuromuscular disorders such as amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS). Besides, some control applications for healthy people are also proposed. Figure 1 shows a brief overview of the BCI system's processing pipeline. Brain signals (e.g., EEG: electroencephalography, MEG: magnetoencephalography, electrocorticography) are recorded first. Secondly, by aggregating the knowledge from neuroscience, stereo-typical brain responses elicited by users' mental tasks are detected with signal processing and machine learning techniques to estimate users' intentions. In this abstract, we introduce three major BCIs. (1) motor-imagery (MI) BCI detects the fluctuation of the power of the EEG signal induced by imagining a particular type of movement (e.g., opening and closing a hand). (2) visual BCI detects stereo-typical EEG responses induced by users' selective attention to the visual stimuli. (3) auditory BCI detects stereo-typical EEG responses induced by users' selective attention to the auditory stimuli. Although many types of BCIs have been proposed, not many can be working with ALS patients. To fill this gap, it is necessary to combine knowledge from many fields, i.e., neuroscience, signal processing, machine learning, and so on, to realize BCIs that are high-performance, high-usability, and high-reliability.

Figure 1. Processing pipeline of BCI system.